

BB-2208 Human Resource Management

Individual Assignment 2

Muhammad Wa'ie Bin Haji Abdul Rashid

19B1086

Table of content	
Abstract	3
Introduction	3
The Guest Model	4
Commitment Based	4
Advantages and Disadvantages	6
Methodology	6
Eco Nadi Agrobiz	6
The Beginning	7
Vision and Mission	7
Challenges	8
Recommendation	9
Conclusion	10
References	11

Abstract

The Agricultural industry in Brunei has made its progress after it declined in 1929 when oil was discovered. In recent years His Majesty the Sultan and Yang Di-Pertuan of Brunei Darussalam has underlined the significance of accomplishing food security and independence which will boost the progress in the agricultural industry. It is however the farmers in Brunei Darussalam are still facing some challenges in venturing into agriculture. This study was carried out on Eco Nadi Agrobiz to determine whether the existing model of Human Resource Management can help to resolve the problem faced by the local agriculture company and achieving their goals. There are four common models of Human Resource Management namely the Guest model, the Harvard model, the Fombrun model, and the Warwick model. This study will be focusing on the Guest model approach.

Introduction

The models of human resource management were created for the purpose of guiding the organization to utilize its human capital to its full potential in order to achieve the organization's goal. Human resource management is a strategic approach on recruiting and selecting new worker as well as concerning the workers' welfare, be it organizational, societal, functional or personal in the organization. Different models have its own unique way of approach with the same objectives, that is to gain a competitive advantage and maximizing its workers' performance. Following are the best-known Human resource management models:

1. The Guest model
2. The Harvard model
3. The Fombrun model
4. The Warwick model

The Guest model

This Human Resource Management approach was developed by David Guest in 1997 and claimed to be a superior than the other model during that time. It is based on the 'soft' approach to human resources. Soft approach is the treatment towards the employees based on emotion and treats the employees as the key resource in the business with value and source of competitive advantage. In contrast, hard approach is where they treat the employees as an asset like a machinery (Task-focused). The focus of Guest's model is to develop a 'commitment based' organization, thus making employee to work more efficiently and functioning well towards the organization. It emphasizes on high levels of trust, commitment and respect between organization and employees. Encouraging its employees to actively participate and share common goals and values. The employees will then show a willingness to go on extra effort in order to benefit the organization.

Commitment based

Commitment based Human Resource practices would increase the predominance of shared values and objectives as it practices team-based work plan and organization-based compensation and rewards which urge the employee to focus on organizational and team achievements dependent on organization execution (Collins & Smith, 2006). As Guest emphasizes on a commitment based Human Resource Management, the strategic management of an organization and Human Resource Management needs to be correlated; The Human Resource Management needs to recruit suitable personnel to make sure the strategic objectives of the organization are accomplished. It has better flexibility within the organization and devolution of authority; the employees understand the need to achieve the strategic objectives of the organization and therefore they are willing to take on extra tasks. Furthermore, the values and respects the employees gain makes them more eager to help the organization reaching their goals.

The Guest model of Human resource management have a sequence 6 dimensions of analysis:

1. Human Resource Management Strategy

Strategy that is being utilized are differentiation, innovation, focuses quality and cost reduction.

2. Human Resource Management Practices

Selection, training, appraisal, reward, job design and involvement are the practices being carried out in this model.

3. Human Resource Management Outcomes

The possible outcomes are high level of commitment, high quality of work given from the employee, and flexibility as in willingness to do extra tasks.

4. Behaviour Outcomes

The results from attending the training and activities occurred inside the organization which promotes the development of the employees' behavior. The improvement in effort and motivation, co-operation, involvement, and organizational citizenship.

5. Performance Outcomes

Can be measured through different metrics within the organization; Greater quality, High productivity and innovation. Organization will have low amount of employees' absentee, low rate of turnover, less conflict and customer complaint as the employees provides high quality performance for the organization

6. Financial Outcomes.

Generating more profit and high return on investment results from the higher quality performance provided by the employees.

Advantages and disadvantages

The advantages of this approach outweigh more than the disadvantages. To set out upon, there are various advantages of this Guest model. By using this approach, the growth in efficiencies of employees can be acknowledge with the flexibility in ways of executing the tasks and working hour being allowed to. The flexibility gives the employees some sort of freedom in doing their work and less restriction bring into effect (Christensen and Schneider, 2010). With the various practices been carried out, the performance and the behaviour tends to be in a higher quality; greater motivation, the eagerness to work, high level of participation, better communication and cooperation, lesser absentees in the organization and low turnover rate. All of that positivity brings toward achieving the organization's goal, favourable financial outcome and positive organizational citizenship. Furthermore, as the organization being strategic in their Human Resource Management, it will cut some unnecessary cost and reduce wastage.

The disadvantages lie on the expense of the practices; high expense on the employees' training and development. One of the possible reasons for the employees to provide better quality of work is to seek for a promotion as a reward. Promotion links to an increase in salary and thus adding expenses to the organization/company.

Methodology

The purpose of this analysis is to determine whether the Guest Model is present or can be used to tackle the challenges faced by the local agricultural company named Eco Nadi Agrobiz. Most of the information data was collected and retrieved from a book titled "*Inspiring Agripreneurs of Brunei*"

Eco Nadi Agrobiz

Eco Nadi Agrobiz is a local chilli plantation located in Sinaut Agriculture Development Area, Kampong Sinaut, Tutong District, Brunei Darussalam. It runs on a four-hectare farm by Haji Mohd Ayub Bin Haji Suhaili and Khairuddin bin Mohammad and was established in November 2016. Eco Nadi Agrobiz produces chilli for the local market. It also utilizing the fertigation system, which is the combination of fertilizer and irrigation; a simple process where the fertilizer is being added into the irrigation system.

Before the establishment of Eco Nadi Agrobiz, both Haji Mohd Ayub and Khairuddin runs their own farms in Kampong Bukit Udal and Kampong Bangungos. With the skills and experiences they both possess, in November 2017, Eco Nadi Agrobiz received recognition from the Agriculture and Agrifood Department

under the Ministry of Primary Resources and Tourism and was awarded with Brunei Good Agricultural Practice (Brunei GAP) certificate. Brunei GAP is a national standard for vegetable and fruit crops set by the Department of Agriculture and Agrifood in 2014. The purpose for Brunei GAP's implementation is to encourage integrated cultivation techniques in order to enhance farm productivity together with greater quality and safe products for the locals.

The beginning

It was Khairuddin bin Mohammad, a partner and a childhood friend of Haji Mohd Ayub Bin Haji Suhaili when they were living in their old town neighbourhood, who gave an idea to wander into agribusiness. During Haji Ayub's time working in both government and private sector, he got to a point where he felt like he should be contributing something back to the nation. He decided to provide food security to the nation as he might suspect food security is one of the keys to attain sustainable growth. Haji Mohd Ayub also went to Malaysia to gain more knowledge regarding farming from more experienced farmers.

The challenges he faced during the early stage of setting up the business is adapting to a very different environment; working under the scorching heat for hours that could easily change individual's mindset to quitting this agribusiness if the individual is not very determine. Despite those challenges, the support from his spouse, children and loved ones is what made him able to pull through.

Vision and Mission

With Eco Nadi Agrobiz already considered a success agrobusiness, the owner of Eco Nadi Agrobiz, Haji Ayub, now is focusing on the Bruneian youth productivity. It can be clearly seen that most farmer in Brunei are the ageing population. He wanted to see whether the youth can venture and help the agriculture industry in Brunei Darussalam in order to achieve the Brunei Vision 2035. Haji Ayub had somewhat contributed to the Brunei Vision 2035; organizing a study tour for the youth to gain knowledge on agriculture and exposure with a hope for the youth to be interested in agriculture. He even partially funded an agriculture classes for the Raja Isteri Pengiran Anak Saleha Secondary School to participate in. The knowledge that the student obtained can be then use in the future if they decided to venture into agriculture industry. Another contribution was conducting a programmes for the special needs' children of Pusat Bahagia and Raja Isteri Pengiran Anak Saleha School in Tutong. He's hopeful that these kids one day can be self-reliant and not relying entirely on their guardian.

The second mission of Eco Nadi Agrobiz is to change the negative impression towards the Malay entrepreneurship skills and proving that Bruneian Malays can be successful in venturing into agricultural industry. Haji Ayub sometimes frustrated and profoundly disheartened on the way people disparaging on farmers and belittle them.

Challenges

- Seeking support; Haji Ayub had some problems in searching aid for his drives. He allows students to do their internship in his agriculture company on the fertigation system. It is however he's unable to find a support in terms of accommodation for the students to stay. Otherwise the students have to commute every day. He had to cancel his agricultural programme due to lack of support.
- Infrastructure; In terms of infrastructure, their land is not suitable for making high quality product but good enough to do their daily agriculture activity. Another problem is not having a well construct irrigation system for the farmers to receive a consistent amount of water supply.
- Finance; According to Haji Ayub, most of the ambitious and agripreneurs enthusiast are not wealthy and more often than not are lacking of funds to invest. They are having difficulties in finding investors and did not have access to the financial support as banks are most likely reluctant to provide loan due to security reasons and the farmers inconsistent income. Haji Ayub also stated that regardless how passionate the young farmers are, for them to try entering this agribusiness without the financial support is impractical.

Recommendation.

To start with, Eco Nadi Agrobiz needs to be strategic in achieving their goals and tackling the challenges they are facing. Contributing back to the country by solving the food insecurity is one of their goal. Diversifying its agricultural product can help solving their food insecurity concern as they only grow chilli as their production for domestic market. Diversification provide variety of choices and creating more supplies of crops to the domestic market. If executing it accurately, it will give a big exposure of the company's brand and increase in profit.

By diversifying its production, it will create more tasks for the farmer. This is where the second step of the six dimensions on the Guest model comes in; Human Resource Management practices. The Human Resource department of Eco Nadi Agrobiz can hire new farmers who's an expert on handling the new crops. If they see hiring new farmer could increase their expenses, another alternative is providing training for the existing farmer in handling the crops. Providing incentives or rewards to the farmer could increase their production and work quality. Thus, creating positive behaviour outcome for the employee. They could even try hiring the special needs children since one of Haji Ayub's goal is wanting the special needs children to be self-reliant.

Hiring experts can help resolve the problem faced by Eco Nadi Agrobiz. They can hire an irrigation specialist to fix their irrigation system problem. In a case of low water supply, place water tanks around the farm.

The major challenge that they're facing is insufficient funds. If the diversification were done correctly, they may earn a lot of profit and thus providing more funds for the company. Another option is to hire an expert negotiator for the company. This might increase the possibility of the company to receive a financial backing, bank loans, or even investors.

Conclusion

It can be seen that the Guest model approach is not present in Eco Nadi Agrobiz. It is however the Guest model can be applied to tackle some of the challenges faced by the company; being strategic in achieving their goals, recruiting suitable applicant or providing training course for the farmer for the diversification project, providing rewards to achieve maximum productivity and high-quality product, and hiring negotiator expert to help them getting the financial support. All of these would bring a positive outcome in terms of behaviour, performance, and company's profit.

References

- Musa, S. F. P. D. H., Pg Hj Idris, P. S. R., & Basir, K. H. (2020). Inspiring Agripreneurs of Brunei. UNISSA Press, Universiti Islam Sultan Sharif Ali.
- Ruzgar, N., & Ulgen, B. (2018). The Effect Of Human Resources Management Models On Employees' Perception Of Their Managers' Humor Styles. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 7(12). doi:10.6007/ijarbss/v7-i12/3618
- Ghosh, D., & Gurunathan, L. (2015, October 21). Do commitment based human resource practices influence job embeddedness and intention to quit? Retrieved November 07, 2020, from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0970389615000968>
- Mr. Vishal Tiwari " Adoption of HRM Practices: A Practical Model- Case Study of a hotel". *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, Vol. 21, No. 4, 2019, pp. -.59-63
- Kukreja S. (2018, December 24). Human Resource Management Models. Retrieved October 26, 2020, from <https://www.managementstudyhq.com/hrm-models.html>
- Assignment on Guest Model – Locus Assignment Help. (n.d.). Retrieved October 26, 2020, from <https://www.locusassignments.com/solution/assignment-guest-model>
- Hard-and-soft-hrm. (2020, October 30). Retrieved November 4, 2020, from <https://www.brighthr.com/articles/hris/hard-and-soft-hrm/>
- Truss, C. (1999). Soft and Hard Models of Human Resource Management. *Strategic Human Resource Management*, 40-58. doi:10.1093/acprof:oso/9780198782049.003.0002
- Ghosh, D., & Gurunathan, L. (2015). Do commitment based human resource practices influence job embeddedness and intention to quit? *IIMB Management Review*, 27(4), 240-251. doi:10.1016/j.iimb.2015.09.003
- Unit 3 HRM Guest Model Assignment: Assignment Writing Service. (n.d.). Retrieved November 4, 2020, from <https://www.locusassignments.com/solution/unit-3-hrm-guest-model-assignment>
- Advantage and disadvantage of hard and soft hrm , HR Management. (n.d.). Retrieved November 04, 2020, from <http://www.expertsmind.com/questions/advantage-and-disadvantage-of-hard-and-soft-hrm-30141009.aspx>
- Guest, D. E. (2017). Human resource management and employee well-being: Towards a new analytic framework. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 27(1), 22-38. doi:10.1111/1748-8583.12139

Looise, Jan Kees. (2004). Innovating Organizations and HRM: A conceptual Framework. Management Revue. 15. 277-288.